

A Focus On SDG Target For The Prevention Of Undernourishment

Abinaya K¹, Pavan Kumar K.N.A¹, Vaibhavalakshmi N¹, Thivya jasmine J¹,
Aadil Ahmed Irshath¹, Raghuraman D R S² and Anand Prem Rajan^{1*}

¹School of Biosciences and Technology, Vellore Institute of Technology, Vellore 632014, Tamil Nādu, India

²School of Mechanical Engineering, Vellore Institute of Technology, Vellore 632014, Tamil Nādu, India

***Corresponding Author**

Anand Prem Rajan

Professor

School of Biosciences and Technology (SBST),

Vellore Institute of Technology (VIT),

Vellore 632014, Tamil Nadu, India

Abstract: Undernourishment seen prevalently all around the World, Initiation of Sustainable Developmental Goals (SDGs) by the UN's Economic and Social Affairs Department's 2030 Strategy encourages the prevention of undernourishment. The Food and Agriculture organization, focuses on this framework which contributes to the SDG target indicators established by all the member countries of the United Nations in 2015, which must be accomplished by 2030, to put an end to hunger and secure access to food for all people, especially the underprivileged and those in risky situations, including infants to have a safe, nourishing and sufficient diet throughout the year, But major problem in achieving this target is disturbance in food supply chain by various causes this makes the food unavailable to the target population and leads to the undernourished population increase. In this review the prevalence and various causes of undernourishment among different countries in world will be seen and focuses on the disruptions in food supply chain which has been a great challenge for achieving the target of zero hunger and possible solutions for the improvement of the supply chain with the help of social entities and its development is provided.

Keywords: Undernourished, poverty, COVID 19, SDG targets, indicators, food supply chain, social entities.

I. INTRODUCTION

World population crossed billions according to projections, now eight billion in 2023, subsequently increasing to 8.5 billion near 2030, will be 9.7 billion by 2050, and a total of 10.9 billion in 2100 [1]. Also, more than 150 million people around world experienced hunger during 2020 as the COVID-19 pandemic approached, after remaining largely steady from 2014 to 2019, the overall incidence regarding malnutrition climbed to roughly 9.9 percentage in 2020 and the additional statistical uncertainty, between 720 and 768 to 811 million people worldwide experienced hunger during 2021 [2, 3]. When an individual does not consume enough energy and nutrients to meet their needs for maintaining good health, they are said to be undernourished. In the following pages undernourishment will be used interchangeably [4].

Undernourishment will be discussed in terms of communities where people cannot able to aid food that is nutritious required for maintaining proper health due to a number of issues, including economic social and environmental ones, this leads to cause of many diseases and disorders even death of a person causing social impact in a community. So, in order to tackle this problem a Sustainable developmental goal specifically Goal 2 adopted by members of United Nations, implemented targets and its indicators which focuses on the prevention of the undernourishment. Even though all these have been come into action but it does not reach the target population and significantly reduce the undernourishment in this case supply chain is one potential factor that could explain why inadequate supply chains result in food shortages among the population. The inequality in the wealth among the lower-income and middle-income countries because of the economy, severe insecurity in food, international trade, climatic shocks, and pandemic situations affects the supply chain. Thereby this study provides the outline of actions that need to be taken and policies that should be maintained in accordance to SDG to make it possible for the prevention of undernourishment [5].

II. PREVALENCE OF UNDERNOURISHMENT

About 720 million to eight hundred and eleven million individuals globally experienced hunger in 2020, an increase of about 161 million from the previous year. Additionally, in 2020, an astounding 2.4 billion individuals, or over thirty percent of the total globe's population, had mild to serious food insecurity and lacked everyday access to a sufficient diet. Around the world, 22.0 percent of kids under the age of five suffered with wasting and stunting during the year 2020[6]. COVID-19 has rekindled the situation by increasing prevalence of undernourishment and large imbalance in the income recovery has been seen in the countries. In 2021 more than half of the people in a population of about 425 million in Asia and more than one third about 278 million people in Africa will be affected by hunger. In many sub regions, and in Caribbean, Africa and Latin America the PoU continued to rise in 2021. Since 2014 and in the beginning of the COVID-19 epidemic, the number of individuals who go hungry and experience a shortage of food has been steadily increasing. These increasing rates have been made far greater by the COVID-19 issue, which additionally made all types of malnutrition worse overall, especially in youngsters [7]. The largest worldwide food emergency since the end of the Second World War is being brought on by the conflict in Ukraine, which continues to disrupt food supply systems around the world [8].

By 2030, Goal 2 of the SDG aims to end all forms of hunger, with a particular emphasis on lowering the prevalence of undernourishment by introducing targets (Figure 1) and its associated indicators (Table 1) focussing on undernourishment.

ROLE OF SDG ON THE PREVENTION OF UNDERNOURISHMENT

Figure 1: Goal 2 targets (Goal 2 | Department of Economic and Social Affairs, 2015).

SDG TARGET 2 INDICATORS	
<p>Indicator 2.1.1 is the predominance of undernourishment. the predominance of undernourishment is the share of the populace with a caloric admissions which is deficiently to meet least prerequisites for a solid life. least prerequisites change by person based on age, gender, weight, activity levels and so change by nation depending on the socioeconomics of its populace, dispersions for person are taken under consideration for this degree. Objective: conclusion starvation by 2030, this implies dispensing with undernourishment for all (Goal 2 Department of Economic and Social Affairs, 2015).</p>	<p>Indicator 2.2.1 is the predominance of hindering among children beneath 5 a long time of age. stunting speaks to serious ailing health as is clear when a child has as well moo tallness for age. a child is hindered when their tallness for age is 2 or more standard deviations underneath the middle of the world wellbeing organization (WHO) child development measures. objective ; by 2030 conclusion all shapes of malnutrition ,including accomplishing by 2030, the universally concurred targets on hindering and squandering in children beneath 5 a long time of age (Goal 2 Department of Economic and Social Affairs, 2015).</p>

Table 1: SDG target indicators (Goal 2 | Department of Economic and Social Affairs, 2015)

STRATEGIES CONTRIBUTES TO SDG ACROSS COUNTRIES

The impoverished suffer from undernourishment because they consume foods which is energy rich but lacking in nutrition because they are getting it at low cost, so if these people get nutritious diet at low cost, undernourishment can be prevented. Priority seeks to reduce under nutrition and eradicating it, along with a nutritious diet and a nutritious food, which is essential to preventing illness. A 2020 Global nutrition report gives an information about the steps and the strategies that can be employed which helps to outreach the vision of the SDG targets it is stated that A significant obstacle to addressing undernutrition is the high expense of many nutrient-dense foods in populations most at risk for it, which calls for urgent policy attention. Improving the affordability of nutrient-rich foods, both for the economy as a whole and for the poorest families, should be one of the main goals of pro-equity, nutrition-conscious food policies. This could be accomplished at the level of the entire economy by lowering prices through enhanced agricultural and trade strategies. Targeted income support, nutritional aid and agricultural development programmes that promote diversification and the consumption of home-grown foods could all help make food more affordable for the poorest families. Efforts to increase nutritional knowledge among current and future carers are justified by crucial significance of providing nutrient-dense foods to infants and early children, also expectant and nursing mothers. The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and the 2025 global nutrition targets can only be met with a thorough and multifaceted strategy that ensures interventions are directed towards those who are most in need. Based on the following guiding principles, such a strategy should cover several industries and be supported by increased resources and targeting[9]. The FAO initiated "Freedom from hunger campaign" puts efforts, by encouraging the developing nations to examine the root causes of food shortages and malnutrition and come up with long-term solutions [10].

In many countries there are strategies that have been followed in order to provide a nutritional supply to the people and helps in preventing undernutrition which contributes to the SDG targets. a programme of conditional cash transfers in Mexico called as PROSPERA (formerly known as Progresas and Oportunidades) is well-known across the world for its achievements in eradicating poverty and enhancing the recipients' physical and nutritional well-being. PROS- PERA, despite not being a nutrition-specific programme, provides a free nutritional supplement for young children, pregnant women, and nursing mothers. It also includes a cash transfer that is based on the recipient household taking several activities to improve health and nutrition. In many parts of Africa, Genetically Modified food has been accepted with interesting outcomes, many nations have not yet agreed to try this novel technique, which may offer a cure for this ailment, or they are still against it. Despite compelling evidence of its safety, the use of genetically modified foods remains controversial in most of the countries across the world[11]. Country Ethiopia has made a great progress in the reduction of child mortality by the reduction of undernutrition by introducing several programmes and practices, while in Ethiopia the universal practice of breast feeding in an extended period of time with 92% of mothers continuing to breastfeed their children at age one and 76% at age two even though the exclusive breastfeeding period is until 6 months. Another programme compares community-based participatory nutrition promotion interventions given by non-profit organisations to current government nutrition initiatives. Compared to the control group, children in the intervention regions had a decreased rate of undernutrition of stunting and underweight, according to government programmes alone[12].

East Asia and the Pacific should take following actions: The seminar served as a forum for debate on how to expand on existing So that extremely malnourished children can receive prompt and efficient treatment at scale, national systems should establish national capacity and partnerships for both treatment and prevention. It gave governments general guidelines for incorporating and institutionalising SAM treatment inside the healthcare system. Representatives from several nations discussed numerous commitments and ideas with the other attendees, Government and UNICEF officials also created a framework of action for the short term (2015) and long term (2016) that included objectives, initiatives, partners, and the necessary assistance. This meeting report includes these frameworks (section 4). The following were the main recommendations and activities made during the meeting, starting with the prevention Both the Acute malnutrition treatment and prevention must be addressed. Prevention is the first action, and additional work is required to identify the factors that contribute to SAM and MAM situations that persist in each environment as well as to customise and record procedures. IYCF practises need to be strengthened as the first line of defence, with a focus on enhancing complementary feeding by making healthy meals more accessible and affordable (incl. food that is locally available). As treatment alone will not address wasting, links with nutrition-sensitive programmes for prevention must be enhanced. Beyond the silos of nutrition, we need to think. MAM management strategies for most development situations, it is important to select IYCF and illness prevention interventions as the most effective MAM management strategies. It can also be necessary to distribute money and specialised nutritional foods according to the context. Advocacy is in order to effectively address the policy and advocacy components of SAM prevention and treatment, it is necessary to obtain a variety of sources of evidence, work with partners, and develop consensus. Two key campaign messages are to reframe SAM as a disease and to identify acute malnutrition as a contributor to stunting. Protocols are necessary to contextualise protocols, guidelines, and frameworks in order to make them into authorised policies. The four service components (inpatient, outpatient, community engagement, and MAM management) must be accurately reflected in IMAM protocols, which must include both technical and operational elements. IMAM protocols must be made simpler, more approachable, and useful. A vision for scaling up is required, along with a gradual yet integrated strategy. Services needed to be scaled up, institutionalised, and made more resilient in both humanitarian and development contexts. IMAM also must be fully institutionalised within the health service system. Also, it's important to make sure high prevalence and high incidence SAM areas are targeted in order to create resilient services, particularly in high-risk areas (such as those prone to emergencies). System strengthening used to prevent and manage SAM in a sustainable manner, systems thinking must be used. Integrating and providing adequate coverage require systems thinking. Instead than focusing on a single component, it examines the entire system (or a set of parts). It aids in gaining understanding of interconnections, synergies, and unforeseen consequences that may have positive outcomes. Also, it aids in long-term, comprehensive planning, which is crucial for fostering sustainability. Information and management systems need to be improved. It's essential to get the right information and apply it correctly. The application and modification of the bottleneck analysis method can improve the breadth and quality of services. It is hoped that the future report would show an acceleration of treatment scale-up, and all nations are urged to work towards a 2015 NutriDash database that provides a significantly more complete picture. Community mobilisation with a focus on optimising the use of current platforms and infrastructure to incorporate SAM prevention, screening, and follow-up, opportunities to establish community systems and empower communities should be taken

advantage of. In the absence of community-based structures and initiatives into which IMAM may be included, service delivery at the level of health facilities must be carried out. Costs should be taken into consideration to incorporate the expense of treating acute malnutrition into various national and sub national financial systems. Products are heavy burden nations should consider domestic RUTF production. It was suggested that a taskforce be established. The Supply Division of UNICEF will offer additional assistance. SAM products must be listed on lists of essential medications. The management of the supply chain must also be enhanced. There are various factors which affects the food supply chain makes the food unavailable or insufficient for the people which can lead to the undernourishment (UNICEF 2015) [13, 14].

II. CAUSES OF DISRUPTION IN THE SUPPLY CHAIN

In terms of undernourishment, the worldwide food supply system is one of the main causes where the lack of an appropriate food supply system can create an increase in undernourishment among the population. There are some disturbances in the food supply chain which make food not available for the people ("The State of Food Security and Nutrition in the World 2021") [15]. One of the main factors contributing to the recent increases in world hunger and catastrophic food crises is climate variability and extremes. Climate variability is evolving, and Extremes are adversely influencing all aspects of (Food accessibility, use, availability and stability) while bolstering other fundamental reasons for child malnutrition, health services, care and nourishment, and ecological safety. Also causes the food insecurity, it is dangerous therefore there are more cases of malnutrition today because livelihoods and assets that support them, particularly of the impoverished are more susceptible and exposed to extremes and evolving climate variability [16]. The food industry has noticed the different effects of rapidly spreading COVID-19 on each link in its supply chain, including the affected workforce at the industrial level, raw material supply from agricultural, food ingredients, and intermediate food products, trade & logistics, demand-supply volatility and uncertain consumer demand at foodservice outlets from other factors. Affected areas of the food industry include distribution, production, and inventories. Those who are affected and work in agricultural farms, food beverage production and processing facilities and distribution networks are currently promoting an outbreak of COVID-19. There is a chance that the coronavirus will spread through product outputs as trade takes place between regions and at different stages of development, which raises concerns about food safety (Prakash, "Impact of COVID-19 on Food Supply Chain") [17]. The newest UN projections (SOFI 2020) indicate that in 2019 saw a rise in the number of hungry people by 10 million from the previous year and by nearly 60 million over the previous five years, to 690 million. Due to high costs, a billion people cannot afford to eat a healthy and nourishing diet. By the end of 2020, the COVID-19 pandemic may have contributed to the chronic hunger of an additional 132 million people worldwide. According to the 2020 World Food Crises report released in April, 135 million people in 55 nations and territories were estimated to have experienced severe food insecurity at crisis levels at the end of 2019. In 2019, there were 17 million cases of wasting and 75 million cases of stunting in children. This level of extreme malnutrition and food insecurity has reached crisis proportions since the publication of the report's first edition in 2017 (World Health Organization: WHO, "As More Go Hungry and Malnutrition Persists, Achieving Zero Hunger by 2030 in Doubt, UN Report Warns") [18].

Most recently, FAO and WFP research from July 2020 identified 27 countries as being at the forefront of impending food crises brought on by COVID-19, as the pandemic's knock-on effects worsen pre-existing hunger-related drivers. No region of the world is safe from this threat, and FAO is especially concerned about how the pandemic will affect those who are already suffering from hunger or other crises, like the Desert Locust outbreak in the Horn of Africa and beyond, economic shock and insecurity in Yemen, or the Sahel. The main reasons for local market price increases for different food commodities, particularly in countries already battling hunger and other crises, are local logistical problems or import difficulties. The FAO is concerned about the pandemic's medium- and long-term effects. Countries, particularly those that heavily rely on food imports, may find it challenging to have the necessary resources to buy food given that unemployment rates have increased and the economic effects of COVID-19 will be felt more acutely in the most vulnerable economies [19]. The impoverished suffer from undernourishment because they consume foods which are energy rich but lacking in nutrition because they are getting it at low cost, so if these people get nutritious diets at low cost, undernourishment can be prevented. Priority seeks to reduce this harmful interaction by emphasizing the requirement for nutritious and delicious meal and a goal 2.2 accentuates preventing under nutrition and eradicating it, along with a nutritious diet and a nutritious food, which is essential to preventing illness, a decline in health leads to hospitalization and associated illnesses. Almost 26 nations, mostly in Africa, West Asia, and Asia, rely on Russia and Ukraine for more than 50% of their wheat imports, which together account for 27% of the global wheat market, Russia-Ukraine war 2022 has interrupted the global food supply chain leading to food shortages and price inflation [20]. A 2020 Global nutrition report gives an information about the steps and the strategies that can be employed which helps to outreach the vision of the SDG targets it is stated that A significant obstacle to addressing undernutrition is the high expense of many nutrient-dense foods in populations most at risk for it, which calls for urgent policy attention. Improving the affordability of nutrient-rich foods, both for the economy as a whole and for the poorest families, should be one of the main goals of pro-equity, nutrition-conscious food policies. This could be accomplished at the level of the entire economy by lowering prices through enhanced agricultural and trade strategies. Targeted income support, nutritional aid, and agricultural development programmes that promote diversification and the consumption of home-grown foods could all help make food more affordable for the poorest families. Efforts to increase nutritional knowledge among current and future carers are justified by crucial significance of providing nutrient-dense foods to infants and early children, also expectant and nursing mothers. The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and the 2025 global nutrition targets can only be met with a thorough and multifaceted strategy that ensures interventions are directed towards those who are most in need. Based on the following guiding principles, such a strategy should cover several industries and be supported by increased resources and targeting. The FAO initiated "Freedom from hunger campaign" puts efforts, by encouraging the developing nations to examine the root causes of food shortages and malnutrition and come up with long-term solutions. But nearly 60 years later, not the entire world has seen the fruit of that noble purpose, so by encouraging these campaigns it reduces the percentage of Malnutrition due to undernourishment [21,22].

III. VARIOUS SOCIAL ENTITIES IN IMPROVING FOOD SUPPLY CHAIN

There are many social entities such as social enterprise and non – profit and profit organizations helps in improving the quality of life of the people by providing them a proper food thus the organizations to be developed or already developed has to meet the requirements in improving the supply chain that makes the food available for all the people in a sustainable as well as in an affordable way. Community Food Enterprise (CFE) Limited, is one such company where the members of the West Ham and Plaistow New Deal for Communities (NDC) catchment area formed the award-winning social enterprise Food Business in 2002 it registered charity with its roots in East London and fighting for the poverty over there for 15 years with a aim of developing a sustainable food business through partnerships and interaction with the community and stakeholders, it supports in realising their objective that to run and oversee a socialised food supply chain that is dedicated to providing the greatest fresh fruit and vegetable products at the most competitive prices. Based on this socialised supply chain, they have created a balanced and complete range of creative community-based services and initiatives, working in conjunction with locals, statutory/voluntary organisations, and local enterprises. CFE combats malnutrition by locating food that is not needed and distributing it to front-line organisations that assist those who are facing poverty. This pertains to only East London's homeless population, occupants of sheltered homes, food banks, and emergency response units (Community food enterprise) [23].

Another non-profit company is food matters partnership Ltd it was founded at the year 2003 which is a nationwide charity it works to improve policy, empower individuals, and transform the food system. A more equitable food system is better for both human and environmental health. They think that food is not only at the root of some of our biggest issues—from obesity to food insecurity, waste to climate change but is also a crucial component of the solutions. An equitable food system can be developed by cities, municipalities, and counties. By bringing together decision-makers, corporations, and local communities, the Sustainable Food Places programme seeks to forge "food partnerships" that will reform regulations and advance access to wholesome, sustainable foods for all. Within the Sustainable Food Places Network, the programme offers professional assistance for food partnerships, this includes providing networking assistance, professional counsel, event facilitation, and strategy planning. As the project moves along, our attention is on fostering peer learning among network members while evaluating the Sustainable Food Places model to promote greater engagement and make sure that partnerships are based on participation, inclusiveness, and representation of the community (Food matters) [24].

The World Food Programme (WFP) the largest humanitarian organisation battling hunger on a global scale is one such organisation the WFP runs development programmes to enhance the long-term food security and nutrition of communities in addition to offer emergency food aid in crisis situations like natural disasters or conflict these projects include efforts to increase agricultural productivity link farmers with markets offer children free meals at school and educate them about nutrition (UN World Food Programme) [25].

Oxfam is another charitable organisation that strives to address the fundamental causes of hunger and poverty Oxfam runs efforts to support sustainable agriculture and increase food security in more than 90 countries including programmes that give small farmers access to markets loans and training another organisation that strives to enhance the world's food systems also providing the food that is needed for the people those who are affected by the various natural calamities through partnerships and various management systems with the aim of ending poverty and ending hunger (Oxfam-Borjen project) [26].

The Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation is another organisation that seeks to enhance the world's food systems. Its initiative for agricultural development encourages study of cutting-edge farming and developing its programme into innovative agricultural technologies methods with the goal of raising the productivity and sustainability of small-scale farmers in developing nations (Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation) [27].

Generally these companies and other organizations like them seek to enhance the food supply chains for people who are undernourished through a variety of initiatives, including emergency food aid, agricultural development programmes, and research into cutting-edge methods and technologies.

IV. THE MODEL CONCERNING THE FOOD SUPPLY CHAIN

The business or the social enterprise model which concerns in improving the food supply chain must overcome the following food product quality as well as the social, environmental problems. The food supply chain is fraught with one major peril, Decomposition foods that exceed their expiry dates are a loss for the company This underlines the importance of having procedures in place to safeguard the food and speed up deliveries in the food supply chain, Partners in charge of a food supply chain need to implement best practices and good procedures to ensure that the goods are delivered to the right port within the right time.

WAYS FOR SAFEGUARDING YOUR FOOD PRODUCTS DURING SUPPLY CHAIN PROCESS

Implementing FIFO, it is abbreviated form of first-in and first-out is an invaluable principle in supply chains when dealing with food, Implementation of FIFO stock rotation policies ensures that the food remains fresh. Under this principle, the stocks that arrive first at the warehouse storage facility will be the stocks that are first to leave when the order comes in. As a result, the stocks sent out will still be fresh with enough time to go. Increase in Speed There can be several areas in the order fulfilment process consumes a lot of time, Bottlenecks might be another issue. It is essential that these areas and issues are identified as quickly as possible. Once identified, the proper fixes and procedures should be implemented and the faster means of transport should be chosen wherever possible by speeding up the order fulfilment process it will reduce the likelihood of delivering foods that have gone bad. Another criteria is Utilize Inventory Positioning, the position of the stocks in the storage warehouse can greatly impact the speed with which orders are fulfilled. Multilevel storage racks are certainly a benefit; however, they should be supported by tools and equipment that make it easy to access the goods for order fulfilment. The position of the inventory within the warehouse needs to be chosen with care as well. The technologies in improvement of the supply chain can be utilized such as Implementing IoT (Internet of things) it involves the use of sensors and other technologies to gather data these sensors can be

fitted into the freight boxes and storage areas to monitor the temperature and other aspects of the food products during food supply chain process. Sensors can also be attached to the storage units, racks, and pallets. This way, it becomes extremely easy to know where each product is located as well as the condition it is in. Foods rapidly approaching their expiry dates can be quickly brought to the forefront and dispatched. Special care procedures can be implemented for those foods which are losing their freshness. This is useful even when the freight is in the move. Sensors can keep track of the goods throughout the supply chain. Controlling the temperature is easily the most important aspect of storing food products during the food supply chain. All food products must be maintained at the right temperature to preserve their freshness. As such, the warehouse must have proper refrigeration and temperature control technologies in place. The temperature must be regulated during transport as well [28].

SOCIAL ENTERPRISE CONCERNING THE FOOD SUPPLY CHAIN

Potential ways for social entrepreneurship to advance the food supply chain for the undernourished. Our dietary habits are dangerously out of balance we produce enough food, but 3 billion people cannot afford a healthy diet, and roughly 1 in 10 people still lack enough to eat. In addition, we throw away one-third of all the food that is produced, along with the natural resources used to generate it. We waste a third of the world's food production as well as the resources used to create it. Food insecurity increased as a result of COVID-19, but climate change will make it much worse our food and agricultural systems go beyond what is sustainable for the planet. We exploit the natural resources required for continued production and degrade the soil by prioritising quantity over quality and encouraging farmers to grow mono crops for cheap prices, which causes climate change and extreme weather events. We became aware of the vulnerability of our food systems as the corona virus crisis developed. As consumers confronted bare shelves, we witnessed news reports of food being wasted, milk being spilled, and crops decaying in the fields. Our intricate worldwide supply chains were unable to respond quickly enough to our shifting circumstances. So we have to overcome these problems by providing possible solutions such as encouraging Regenerative agriculture, a stronger voice for farmers, and a shift from low-cost to "true cost" food may develop a stronger food system for people, the earth, and the future. A growing global population demands fairer, more resilient and equitable food systems by make use of the Earth's regenerative power this is essential for overcoming the largest problems of our day, including climate change, biodiversity loss, and environmental degradation. Regenerative farming creates healthy soil that can produce food that is high-quality and nutrient-dense. Additionally, it fosters productive agriculture, healthy communities, and thriving economies rather than deteriorating the land. In order for farmers to produce the food we need today and, in the future, this helps protect their means of subsistence. Strengthen regional and sustainable food systems; strengthening local and circular food systems promotes the retention of essential minerals, nutrients, and natural resources. In addition to offering outstanding environmental solutions, circular agribusinesses also provide employment and lessen a country's reliance on imports. For instance, waste water can be processed to remove significant finite minerals like phosphates. Composting can help important nutrients return to the soil instead of being wasted from food loss and waste. Additionally, bio energy from organic farm waste can be used to run farms and residential buildings. By using black soldier flies to compost waste, for example, new, nature-based technologies can provide a variety of beneficial by-products, such as compost, fertiliser, and animal feed. Support farmers' environmentally friendly decisions and give them a voice. More people will depend on farmers for food than ever as the world's population expands. Making farmers an active part of policy conversations will enable them to lead solutions and be at the forefront of a global regenerative movement. They can contribute to the development of a network of locally relevant goods and services and lessen reliance on patented or chemical inputs. Go from cheap to genuine cost; cheap food is costly for both individuals and the environment. It keeps us trapped in a food system that is not sustainable and costs the world economy a lot of money. The cost of unhealthy diets, land degradation, and biodiversity loss is not taken into account in the current price of food. Agriculture is also a volatile and frequently dangerous industry due to the poor income that farmers receive. To turn things around, we want more informed consumers and governmental policies that place a premium on wholesome foods, a healthy environment, and farmers that engage in regenerative agriculture. Encourage radical cooperation though we have optimism for the future, time is rapidly running out. The obstacles preventing us from changing the way we produce and consume food must be removed immediately. This entails altering perspectives, experimenting, and picking up information quickly. The issue is business as usual, even though we don't yet have all the solutions. We must immediately alter course. Collaboration between farmers, consumers, funders, governments, companies, and NGOs is required for this to be successful. Together, we can create a food system that not only nourishes us but also celebrate life (World Economic forum)[29, 30].

V. CONCLUSION

The prevalence of undernourishment seen in various places across the world it can be expressed in terms of poverty where the people in those areas cannot get a proper meals which leads to the insufficient nutrient intake that causes various diseases as well as disorders where the Sustainable developmental goals (SDGs) targets especially SDG target 2 works on this area where this study particularly focus on the target indicators of zero hunger , Thus several organizations works on realizing this target that contributes to the well-being of the impoverished people by providing them the food of low cost . The undernourishment across the poor countries such as South Africa, Burundi, Nigeria, and three other fragile or highly fragile nations round out the list there is a huge wealth gap among the nations and this should be taken into account while executing the nutritional plans .Interventions, policy, and prevention initiatives should focus on numerous nutrition disparities at once and be poor nutrition-sensitive, especially for areas or populations who are disproportionately affected by malnutrition. High-quality, methodically gathered granular nutrition statistics are urgently required. Even though many plans and policies are already implemented, the strategy enhancement is needed in order to effectively prevent the undernourishment. And a multispectral approach is need and given priority. Even though all the policies have been carried out in order to prevent the undernourishment but these does not reach the target population where the supply chain if affected by the various factors such as climatic changes, pandemic situations, etc. as a result of this leads to the hunger in the countries were affected by, here where under nutrition comes into picture. So, by analysing these situations it is important to have a strategy and the enhancement and the social enterprises and the required plans which is given in this review the consequences of the disturbance in the supply chain, through various anticipated factors and further taking

actions before the occurrence to have a world with a reduction of under nutrition or undernourishment which accomplishes the SDG's target on "Zero hunger".

REFERENCES

- [1] Naheed, Sanober. "An overview of the influence of climate change on food security and human health." *life* 3 (2023): 15.
- [2] Hoddinott, John. "Achieving the SDG's of ending hunger and food insecurity: Issues and options 12 October 2021." (2021).
- [3] FAO, IFAD, UNICEF, WFP and WHO. 2021. In Brief to The State of Food Security and Nutrition in the World 2021.
- [4] Maleta, Ken. "Undernutrition." *Malawi medical journal : the journal of Medical Association of Malawi* vol. 18,4 (2006): 189-205.
- [5] Neufeld, L., et al. "Advance equitable livelihoods: a paper on action track 4." *Science and Innovations* (2021): 143.
- [6] World Health Organization. *The State of Food Security and Nutrition in the World 2021: Transforming food systems for food security, improved nutrition and affordable healthy diets for all. Vol. 2021. Food & Agriculture Org., 2021.*
- [7] FAO, IFAD, UNICEF, WFP and WHO. 2022. *The State of Food Security and Nutrition in the World 2022. Repurposing food and agricultural policies to make healthy diets more affordable. Rome, FAO.*
- [8] Ben Hassen, Tarek, and Hamid El Bilali. "Impacts of the Russia-Ukraine war on global food security: towards more sustainable and resilient food systems?." *Foods* 11.15 (2022): 2301.
- [9] Fanzo, Jessica. "Food Policies' Roles on Nutrition Goals and Outcomes: Connecting of Food and Public Health Systems." *International Food Law and Policy* 213–251. 1 Dec. 2016, doi:10.1007/978-3-319-07542-6_9
- [10] Bunch, Matthew James. "All roads lead to Rome: Canada, the Freedom From Hunger Campaign, and the rise of NGOs, 1960-1980." (2007).
- [11] Ramírez, Viviana. *Relational Well-Being in Policy Implementation in Mexico: The Oportunidades-Prospera Conditional Cash Transfer*. Springer Nature, 2021.
- [12] Aarts, Clara, et al. "How exclusive is exclusive breastfeeding? A comparison of data since birth with current status data." *International Journal of epidemiology* 29.6 (2000): 1041-1046.
- [13] UNICEF. (2015). *Prevention and Treatment of Severe Acute Malnutrition in East Asia and the Pacific Report of a Regional Consultation*.
- [14] Ogobara Dounon, A.; Charle-Cuéllar, P.; Toure, F.; Aziz Gado, A.; Sanoussi, A.; Lazoumar, R.H.; Alain Tchamba, G.; Vargas, A.; Lopez-Ejeda, N. Impact of Integration of Severe Acute Malnutrition Treatment in Primary Health Care Provided by Community Health Workers in Rural Niger. *Nutrients* 2021, 13, 4067.
- [15] World Health Organization. *The state of food security and nutrition in the world 2020: transforming food systems for affordable healthy diets. Vol. 2020. Food & Agriculture Org., 2020.*
- [16] McMichael, Anthony J., and Elisabet Lindgren. "Climate change: present and future risks to health, and necessary responses." *Journal of internal medicine* 270.5 (2011): 401-413.
- [17] Sinha, Shweta, and Mrutyunjay Swain. "Response and resilience of agricultural value chain to COVID-19 pandemic in India and Thailand." *Pandemic Risk, Response, and Resilience* (2022): 363–381. doi:10.1016/B978-0-323-99277-0.00002-4
- [18] Hongguang, Wang. "Basic Conclusions on Global Food Security." *China's Food Security: Strategies and Countermeasures*. Singapore: Springer Nature Singapore, 2023. 175-192.
- [19] Oluwole, Oluwatoyin Bolanle, and Olusola Fatimah Olagunju-Yusuf. "Food and Nutrition Insecurity in Africa: The Primary Drivers and Sustainable Strategies to Improve the Current Status." *Food Security and Safety Volume 2: African Perspectives*. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2022. 265-282.
- [20] Ben Hassen, Tarek, and Hamid El Bilali. "Impacts of the Russia-Ukraine war on global food security: towards more sustainable and resilient food systems?." *Foods* 11.15 (2022): 2301.
- [21] Herforth, Anna, Andrew Jones, and Per Pinstrup-Andersen. "Prioritizing nutrition in agriculture and rural development: guiding principles for operational investments." (2012).
- [22] Reinhardt, Kristina, and Jessica Fanzo. "Addressing Chronic Malnutrition through Multi-Sectoral, Sustainable Approaches: A Review of the Causes and Consequences." *Frontiers in nutrition* vol. 1 13. 15 Aug. 2014, doi:10.3389/fnut.2014.00013
- [23] Shuman, Michael, Alissa Baron, and Wendy Wasserman. "Community Food Enterprise: Local Success in a Global Marketplace." *Gates Open Res* 3.744 (2019): 744.
- [24] Cabinet Office. "Food matters: Towards a strategy for the 21st century." (2008).
- [25] O'Connor, Daniel, et al. "Living with insecurity: Food security, resilience, and the World Food Programme (WFP)." *Global Social Policy* 17.1 (2017): 3-20.
- [26] Davidson, Joan, Dorothy Myers, and Manab Chakraborty. *No time to waste: Poverty and the global environment*. Oxfam GB, 1992.
- [27] Herdt, Robert W. "People, institutions, and technology: a personal view of the role of foundations in international agricultural research and development 1960–2010." *Food Policy* 37.2 (2012): 179-190.
- [28] Sahin, Evren, et al. "Ensuring supply chain safety through time temperature integrators." *The international journal of logistics management* 18.1 (2007): 102-124.
- [29] Nicolétis, Évariste, et al. "Agroecological and other innovative approaches for sustainable agriculture and food systems that enhance food security and nutrition. A report by the High Level Panel of Experts on Food Security and Nutrition of the Committee on World Food Security." (2019).
- [30] Fanzo, Jessica, et al. "Sustainable food systems and nutrition in the 21st century: a report from the 22nd annual Harvard Nutrition Obesity Symposium." *The American Journal of Clinical Nutrition* 115.1 (2022): 18-33.

UNICEF. (2015). *Prevention and Treatment of Severe Acute Malnutrition in East Asia and the Pacific Report of a Regional Consultation*. <https://www.unicef.org/eap/media/1306/file>

FAO, IFAD, UNICEF, WFP and WHO eBooks, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.4060/cb4474en>.

"Impact of COVID-19 on Food Supply Chain." *FutureBridge*, May 2020, www.futurebridge.com/industry/perspectives-food-nutrition/impact-of-covid-19-on-food-supply-chain/#.

“As More Go Hungry and Malnutrition Persists, Achieving Zero Hunger by 2030 in Doubt, UN Report Warns.” <https://www.who.int/news/item/13-07-2020-as-more-go-hungry-and-malnutrition-persists-achieving-zero-hunger-by-2030-in-doubt-un-report-warns>, 13 July 2020, www.who.int/news/item/13-07-2020-as-more-go-hungry-and-malnutrition-persists-achieving-zero-hunger-by-2030-in-doubt-un-report-warns. Accessed 16 May 2023.

Home | Community Food Enterprise. (2023). Mysite. <https://www.c-f-e.org.uk/>

Seb_Admin. (2023, May 2). Sustainable Food Places - Food Matters. Food Matters. <https://www.foodmatters.org/projects/flagship-projects/sustainable-food-places/>

UN World Food Programme (WFP). (2023.). <http://www.wfp.org/>

The Borgen Project. (2022, October 23). Oxfam International - The Borgen Project. <https://borgenproject.org/tag/oxfam-international/>

Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation. (2023). Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation. <https://www.gatesfoundation.org/>

How to create a more sustainable global food system. (2021, February 16). World Economic Forum. <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2021/02/how-to-create-a-more-sustainable-global-food-system-in-the-wake-of-covid-19/>

5 ways to transform our food systems and save the planet. (2021, March 5). World Economic Forum. <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2021/03/5-ways-transform-food-system-sustainable/>